

Phase-Only Implementation of the Complex Screen Technique for Generating Schell-Model Sources

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Abstract— In this paper, implementation of the complex screen approach for generating partially-coherent Schell-model sources using phase-only control, like that available using commercial-off-the-shelf liquid-crystal spatial light modulators, is presented. Previous techniques for generating Schell-model sources have used phase-only spatial light modulators in combination with amplitude filters to produce partially-coherent fields. Using amplitude filters complicates the optical set-up and significantly reduces the flexibility of the system. Here, both analytically and with simulations, it is shown that both the amplitude and phase of the source field can be manipulated using phase-only control. This contribution removes the need to use amplitude filters, thereby simplifying the optical set-up and increasing the system's flexibility.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The behavior of partially-coherent light has been the subject of extensive research especially in the last 10 years. Numerous theoretical and some experimental studies have been performed examining how partially-coherent light propagates through free space and random media (atmospheric turbulence, biological tissue, and ocean water) [1–5] and scatters from deterministic and random objects [6–10]. These studies, as well as many others, have noted interesting characteristics of partially-coherent light that can possibly be exploited in applications such as free-space optical communications, directed energy, remote sensing, particle manipulation, and etcetera. The interested reader is referred to [1, 11, 12] for very good books and reviews on the subject.

Considering the many possible applications of partially-coherent light, techniques to synthesize partially-coherent sources have naturally followed [1, 11, 13–18]. A large majority of these techniques are focused on synthesizing Gaussian Schell-model sources [1, 19, 20] and their many variants because of their analytical tractability.

The most common way to synthesize a Gaussian Schell-model source is to use a Gaussian amplitude filter and phase-only liquid-crystal spatial light modulator (SLM). The Gaussian amplitude filter is used to create the Gaussian amplitude

profile (better known as the spectral density), while the SLM is used to form the correlation function (better known as the spectral degree of coherence) of the source [15, 16].

As evidenced by the numerous references which employ this approach, the traditional method described above is very well suited for generating Gaussian Schell-model sources; however, it suffers when one wants to synthesize general Schell-model sources. One of the main reasons for this is the traditional approach's use of amplitude filters. If one wants to produce a source with a different spectral density, a new amplitude filter is required. The reliance on amplitude filters to produce the source's spectral density makes the optical set-up more complicated, increases its size or footprint, and significantly reduces the sources that can be generated using the system (i.e., reduces the system's flexibility).

In this paper, a method to synthesize a general Schell-model source that only requires a single phase-only SLM is presented. The method described here utilizes the complex screen approach for generating partially-coherent sources [15, 21]. The complex screen approach manipulates both the amplitude and phase of an initially coherent field. In this way, any Schell-model source can be generated. Previous work employing the complex screen method presented the technique as a simulation-only tool [15, 21]. This is because dynamically controlling both field amplitude and phase in the laboratory is difficult. This limitation of the complex screen approach is addressed here and is the main contribution of this research.

In the next section, the complex screen method for generating Schell-model sources is briefly reviewed. Also included in that section is the process for generating complex screens with the appropriate statistical properties and how both field amplitude and phase can be controlled using a single phase-only SLM. Section 3 proposes and simulates an experimental set-up for synthesizing partially-coherent sources using the complex screen method. A unique Schell-model source, which cannot be easily created using the traditional approach, is generated/simulated to validate the proposed phase-only complex screen technique. Lastly, this paper is concluded with a summary and a brief discussion of future work.

2. METHODOLOGY

Assuming that the source field is wide-sense stationary, a general Schell-model source takes the form

$$W(\rho_1, \rho_2) = \sqrt{S(\rho_1)}\sqrt{S(\rho_2)}\mu(\rho_1 - \rho_2), \quad (1)$$

where W is the cross-spectral density function, S is the spectral density, μ is the spectral degree of coherence, and $\rho = \hat{x}x + \hat{y}y$ [1, 19, 20]. W , S , and μ are, in general,

functions of frequency omitted here for brevity.

Complex Screen Method

A single instance of a complex screen field takes the form

$$U(\boldsymbol{\rho}) = \sqrt{S(\boldsymbol{\rho})}T(\boldsymbol{\rho}), \quad (2)$$

where T is the complex screen and is a sample function drawn from a zero-mean, circular complex Gaussian random process. Taking the autocorrelation of (2) and comparing that result to (1) reveals that

$$\langle T(\boldsymbol{\rho}_1)T^*(\boldsymbol{\rho}_2) \rangle = \mu(\boldsymbol{\rho}_1 - \boldsymbol{\rho}_2). \quad (3)$$

Equation (3) stipulates that any partially-coherent Schell-model source can be generated if $\langle |U|^2 \rangle = S$ and T can be synthesized with an autocorrelation equal to μ .

Generating T

In this section, the process for generating complex screens T is described. Note that this process is described in detail in [15]. A brief summary is provided here for the convenience of the reader.

Let T and \tilde{T} be Fourier transform pairs:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{T}(\mathbf{f}) &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} T(\boldsymbol{\rho}) e^{-j2\pi\mathbf{f}\cdot\boldsymbol{\rho}} d^2\rho \\ T(\boldsymbol{\rho}) &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \tilde{T}(\mathbf{f}) e^{j2\pi\mathbf{f}\cdot\boldsymbol{\rho}} d^2\mathbf{f} \end{aligned}, \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{f} = \hat{\mathbf{x}}f_x + \hat{\mathbf{y}}f_y$ is the spatial frequency vector. Taking the autocorrelation of the above expressions and using (3) yields

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi^T(\Delta\mathbf{f}) &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \mu(\Delta\boldsymbol{\rho}) e^{-j2\pi\Delta\mathbf{f}\cdot\Delta\boldsymbol{\rho}} d^2\Delta\boldsymbol{\rho} \\ \mu(\Delta\boldsymbol{\rho}) &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \Phi^T(\Delta\mathbf{f}) e^{j2\pi\Delta\mathbf{f}\cdot\Delta\boldsymbol{\rho}} d^2\Delta\mathbf{f} \end{aligned}, \quad (5)$$

where Φ^T is the power spectral density of T , $\Delta\boldsymbol{\rho} = \hat{\mathbf{x}}(x_1 - x_2) + \hat{\mathbf{y}}(y_1 - y_2)$, and $\Delta\mathbf{f} = \hat{\mathbf{x}}(f_{x1} - f_{x2}) + \hat{\mathbf{y}}(f_{y1} - f_{y2})$.

The simple relations in (5) are due to the fact that T is a statistically homogeneous random field (i.e., the spatial equivalent of wide-sense stationary). As a result, (5) is the spatial equivalent of the Wiener-Khinchin theorem [22].

Let T be expanded in a Fourier series:

$$T(x, y) = \sum_{m,n} \mathcal{T}_{m,n} \exp\left(j\frac{2\pi}{L}mx\right) \exp\left(j\frac{2\pi}{L}ny\right), \quad (6)$$

where \mathcal{T} are the Fourier series coefficients and L is the physical size of the discrete computational grid in meters. Note that since T are zero-mean, circular complex Gaussian,

so are \mathcal{T} . Taking the autocorrelation of (6) and comparing that relation to the bottom expression in (5) reveals that

$$\langle |\mathcal{T}_{m,n}|^2 \rangle = \Phi^T\left[\frac{m}{L}, \frac{n}{L}\right] \frac{1}{L^2}. \quad (7)$$

Note that $\langle |\mathcal{T}_{m,n}|^2 \rangle$ is the variance of the Fourier series coefficients \mathcal{T} . Since \mathcal{T} are circular complex Gaussian, the real and imaginary parts of \mathcal{T} have equal variances, i.e., $\sigma_{\text{Re}(\mathcal{T})}^2 = \sigma_{\text{Im}(\mathcal{T})}^2 = 1/2 \langle |\mathcal{T}_{m,n}|^2 \rangle$. Thus, a complex screen T can be synthesized by generating an array of zero-mean, unit-variance, circular complex Gaussian random numbers r , multiplying r by $\sqrt{1/2 \langle |\mathcal{T}_{m,n}|^2 \rangle}$, and applying (6), viz.,

$$\begin{aligned} T[i, j] &= \sum_{m,n} r[m, n] \sqrt{\Phi^T\left[\frac{m}{L}, \frac{n}{L}\right] \frac{1}{L^2}} \\ &\quad \exp\left(j\frac{2\pi}{N}mi\right) \exp\left(j\frac{2\pi}{N}nj\right) \end{aligned}, \quad (8)$$

where i, j are the x, y discrete spatial indices, respectively, and N is number of samples per side making up the discrete grid. Note that $L = N\delta$, where δ is the discrete sample spacing in meters. Equation (8) is in the form of a discrete inverse Fourier transform; thus, it is most convenient to use the fast Fourier transform algorithm to synthesize T .

Phase-Only Field Control

Recall that the goal here is to implement the complex screen method for generating partially-coherent Schell-model sources using phase-only control. Since the complex screen method requires that both the amplitude and phase of an initially collimated field be manipulated, a method must be devised to control both amplitude and phase by just manipulating field phase.

This can be achieved by producing a periodic sawtooth phase grating like that shown in Fig. 1, which produces the desired complex screen field in the first diffraction order. By manipulating the grating period and height h , the amplitude and phase of the field in the first diffraction order can be precisely controlled.

It should be noted that phase-only amplitude control has been presented before, most notably in [23–26]. In those references, the expression for the field scattered from a continuous sawtooth grating was reported. Here, the discrete nature of the computational grid (and ultimately the SLM) is considered.

Consider the geometry shown in Fig. 1. The figure depicts a periodic, discrete sawtooth phase grating where each ‘‘pixel’’ (of width d) applies a phase ϕ_n to the transiting field incident from the left. The sawteeth making up the grating are all of height h and comprised of $N + 1$ pixels. For analytical convenience, it is assumed that the structure and incident field are invariant in the y direction. This simplification does not affect the applicability of the result.

Assuming that the incident field uniformly illuminates the grating, the field just to the right of the grating ($z = 0^+$)

Figure 1. Sawtooth phase grating geometry.

takes the form

$$U(x, 0^+) = \sum_{m=0}^M \sum_{n=0}^N \text{rect} \left(\frac{x - nd - m(N+1)d}{d} \right) \exp \left[jkn \frac{h}{(N+1)} \right], \quad (9)$$

where $k = 2\pi/\lambda$ and rect is defined in [27]:

$$\text{rect}(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & |x| < 1/2 \\ 1/2 & |x| = 1/2 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}. \quad (10)$$

The field is observed in the far zone (in practice, achieved using lenses):

$$U(x, Z) \propto \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} U(x', 0^+) \exp \left(-j \frac{k}{Z} xx' \right) dx' \\ \propto d \text{sinc} \left(\frac{k}{Z} \frac{d}{2} x \right) \sum_{m=0}^M \left\{ \exp[-jk\psi_1(x)] \right\}^m, \quad (11) \\ \sum_{n=0}^N \left\{ \exp[-jk\psi_2(x, h)] \right\}^n$$

where $\psi_1 = x(d/Z)(N+1)$, $\psi_2 = x(d/Z) - h/(N+1)$, and $\text{sinc}(x) = \sin(x)/x$. The summations in (11) are recognized as geometric series [28]; thus, (11) simplifies to

$$U(x, Z) \propto d \text{sinc} \left(\frac{k}{Z} \frac{d}{2} x \right) \exp \left[-j \frac{k}{2} (M\psi_1 + N\psi_2) \right] \\ \frac{\sin \left[\frac{k}{2} (M+1)\psi_1 \right] \sin \left[\frac{k}{2} (N+1)\psi_2 \right]}{\sin \left(\frac{k}{2}\psi_1 \right) \sin \left(\frac{k}{2}\psi_2 \right)} \quad (12)$$

The first “sin over sin” expression in (12) determines the x locations of the diffraction orders, i.e., $x_\ell = \ell\lambda Z / [(N+1)d]$. Recall that the field in the first diffraction order $\ell = 1$ is germane. Substituting x_1 into (12) and simplifying yields

$$U(x_1, Z) \propto \exp \left[-j\pi \frac{N}{N+1} \left(1 - \frac{h}{\lambda} \right) \right] \\ \frac{\sin \left[\pi \left(1 - \frac{h}{\lambda} \right) \right]}{\sin \left[\pi \frac{1}{N+1} \left(1 - \frac{h}{\lambda} \right) \right]}, \quad (13)$$

where the other terms have been omitted because they do not depend on the grating height h and therefore are irrelevant.

If $N \rightarrow \infty$, i.e., a continuous sawtooth grating, then

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} U(x_1, Z) \propto \exp \left[-j\pi \left(1 - \frac{h}{\lambda} \right) \right] \\ \text{sinc} \left[\pi \left(1 - \frac{h}{\lambda} \right) \right] \\ = \exp[-jP(h)] H(h) \quad (14)$$

where, again, the factors that do not depend on h have been omitted. This is the expression reported in [23–26] and is correct in the case of a continuous sawtooth phase grating. Equation (14) is an excellent approximation to the true relation in (13) for $N > 4$.

Phase-Only Complex Screen Field U

Applying the above analysis, a phase-only complex screen field can be created in the following manner:

1. Produce a complex screen field instance $U = \sqrt{ST}$, where one is generally free to choose the spectral density S and T is synthesized in the manner outlined above.
2. Find the required sawtooth heights h by solving $h = H^{-1}(|U|)$.
3. Apply

$$\phi[i, j] = \arg \left(\exp \{ j [G(h) + \arg(T) + F(h)] \} \right) \quad (15)$$

to an initially collimated field. Here, G and F are functions that create the two-dimensional sawtooth grating (with the appropriate heights h) and P , respectively. The purpose of F is to remove the unwanted phase [the complex exponential in (14)] imparted to U by the sawtooth G .

The desired complex screen field U is produced in the first diffraction order.

The sawteeth making up the grating contain the same number of pixels $N+1$ (i.e., have the same period); however, in

Figure 2. Proposed experimental set-up for generating Schell-model sources using the phase-only complex screen method—L is lens, I is iris, SP is source plane, FZ is far zone, and SLM is spatial light modulator.

general, their heights h vary. The grating can be applied in the x (as shown in Fig. 1), y , or in both directions. The number of pixels in each sawtooth determines the fidelity of $|U|$ (more is generally better) and the separation of the diffraction orders (fewer pixels provides greater separation). Therefore, N must be chosen such that $|U|$ is of sufficient quality, while providing enough diffraction order separation so that the desired first order can be effectively isolated from the others (typically achieved using a spatial filter).

3. VERIFICATION

Simulation Set-Up

Figure 2 shows a proposed experimental set-up for generating Schell-model sources using the phase-only complex screen approach described above. This system is currently under construction and is therefore simulated here. Light from a 532 nm coherent source is incident on a simulated Holoeye PLUTO SLM—a reflective, phase-only 1920×1080 device with a $8 \mu\text{m}$ pixel pitch. The Holoeye SLM was simulated by applying (15) to an initially collimated field, i.e.,

$$U^{\text{SLM}}[i, j] = \exp(j\phi[i, j]). \quad (16)$$

After being formed as shown in (16), U^{SLM} was zero padded to 2048×2048 for the subsequent fast Fourier transform propagations.

The incident light scatters from the SLM into multiple diffraction orders as depicted. In practice, the SLM is turned to direct the desired first diffraction order toward the sensors.

In simulation, this was achieved by applying a tilt phase [29] to U^{SLM} .

Eight pixels per sawtooth were used to form the grating. This choice produced an accurate $|U|$, while separating the diffraction orders enough such that a spatial filter (described below) could easily isolate the desired first order. The grating was formed in both the horizontal and vertical directions to move the first diffraction order away from the side lobes (oriented in the horizontal and vertical directions) of the zeroth order.

The scattered light then enters a spatial filter composed of two 350 mm lenses and an iris. The iris blocks all orders other than the desired first order. The field at the output of the spatial filter, i.e., the effective source-plane of the system (denoted by a dashed red line labeled SP in Fig. 2), is the complex screen field U . The spatial filter was simulated by Fourier transforming U^{SLM} (with tilt applied) and multiplying the resulting field by a circ function [27] with a 2.5 mm diameter. The spatially filtered field was then Fourier transformed again producing \tilde{U} at the location demarcated in Fig. 2. The irradiance of the field in the source plane was captured using a simulated Lumenera LU125M camera— 1280×1024 with a $6.7 \mu\text{m}$ pitch. The simulated U was interpolated to the Lumenera LU125M camera dimensions. It is clear from (1) and (2) that the source-plane spectral density S can be obtained by averaging the “instantaneous” source-plane irradiances. Thus, collecting and then averaging source-plane irradiances demonstrates how well the phase-only complex screen method produces the desired S .

Lastly, a 1.5 m lens is applied to the source-plane field to form the far-zone pattern of U at the second red dashed line labeled FZ in Fig. 2. This was achieved in simulation by Fourier transforming the complex screen field U . The irradiance of the far-zone field was captured using a simulated Lumenera LU125M camera. Again, the simulated far-zone U was interpolated to the Lumenera LU125M camera dimensions. It is relatively straightforward to show that the far-zone spectral density is predominately driven by the source-plane spectral degree of coherence μ [1, 19, 20]. Thus, collecting and then averaging the far-zone irradiances demonstrates how well the phase-only complex screen method produces the desired μ .

For the simulation results presented below, 5,000 complex screen field instances were propagated and processed in the manner described above to produce 5,000 source-plane and far-zone irradiances. These irradiances were then averaged to compute the source-plane and far-zone spectral densities, respectively.

Results

To validate and demonstrate the flexibility of the phase-only complex screen method presented here, a unique Schell-model source was generated which had source-plane and far-zone spectral densities in the shapes of the IEEE Aerospace Conference call for papers cover page and logo, respectively.

Figure 3 shows the results—(a) and (b) show the original IEEE Aerospace Conference call for papers cover page and logo, respectively, while (c) and (d) show the simulated phase-only complex screen cover page (source-plane spectral density) and logo (far-zone spectral density), respectively.

Overall, the complex screen results compare quite well with the original images. Especially noteworthy is the excellent

Figure 3. Phase-only complex screen method simulation results—(a) original IEEE Aerospace Conference call for papers cover page, (b) original IEEE Aerospace Conference logo, (c) simulated complex screen source-plane spectral density, and (d) simulated complex screen far-zone spectral density.

complex screen logo result [Fig. 3(d)], where all the features in the original image [Fig. 3(b)] are clearly reproduced. The complex screen cover page result [Fig. 3(c)] is not as impressive as the logo result; however, spacecraft features (e.g., the antenna reflector and feed), Pluto, Charon, and some of the lettering are visible.

Obviously, a partially-coherent source like that synthesized above is of little practical use. The goal here was to choose a source that demonstrated proof of concept with no specific application in mind. The results shown in Fig. 3 achieve this goal.

4. CONCLUSION

In this paper, implementation of the complex screen method for generating partially-coherent Schell-model sources using phase-only control was presented. The analytical development of the approach was presented in Section 2. The section contained a brief description of the complex screen method, the process for synthesizing complex screens T , and how to control both amplitude and phase by just manipulating field phase. Section 3 presented simulation results to validate and demonstrate the flexibility of the proposed method. The Schell-model source that was generated had source-plane and far-zone spectral densities in the shapes of the IEEE Aerospace Conference call for papers cover page and logo, respectively. The agreement between the phase-only complex screen results and the original images was quite good and successfully demonstrated proof of concept. The next step is to validate the phase-only complex screen method experimentally. This is currently in work.

The phase-only complex screen method will be useful in any application where control over beam shape and coherence is desired. These applications include free-space optical communications, remote sensing, directed energy, medicine, particle manipulation, and manufacturing.

The views expressed in this paper are those of the authors and do not reflect the official policy or position of the US Air Force, the Department of Defense, or the US Government.

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BIOGRAPHY

Milo W. Hyde IV(S'10—M'10—SM'12) received the B.S. degree in computer engineering from the Georgia Institute of Technology, Atlanta, GA in 2001 and the M.S. and Ph.D. degrees in electrical engineering from the Air Force Institute of Technology, Wright-Patterson Air Force Base (AFB), Dayton, OH in 2006 and 2010, respectively. From 2001 to 2004, Dr. Hyde was a maintenance officer with the F-117A Nighthawk, Holloman AFB, Alamogordo, NM. From 2006 to 2007, he was a government researcher with the Air Force Research Laboratory, Wright-Patterson AFB. He is currently an Associate Professor in the Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering at the Air Force Institute of Technology. His current research interests include electromagnetic material characterization, guided-wave theory, scattering, and optics. Dr. Hyde is a member of the International Society for Optical Engineering, the Optical Society of America, the American Geophysical Union, the Directed Energy Professional Society, and the Applied Computational Electromagnetics Society.